

The Impact of Financial Literacy on Investor Well-Being: Exploring the Mediating Role of Financial Behavior and Quality of Life

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Abstract: This study explores the impact of financial knowledge on investors' behavior and overall well-being in the rapidly changing financial sector and economy. By analyzing key indicators of quality of life and behavioral factors through Structural Equation Modeling on a sample of 243 retail investors, the research identifies the significant influence of financial knowledge on short-term behavior and overall well-being. The findings underscore the importance of targeted financial education programs to empower investors and address financial stress, ultimately leading to improved quality of life and overall financial satisfaction. Policymakers and practitioners can leverage these insights to design effective interventions, fostering financial well-being and informed decision-making among individuals in today's interconnected financial landscape.

Keywords: Financial Knowledge, Investors' Behavior, Quality of Life, Structural Equation Modeling, Financial Education

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1. Introduction

In today's rapidly changing financial landscape, it is crucial to assess whether individuals possess the necessary skills to navigate the complexities of financial decisions they encounter daily. Understanding the gap between their current financial knowledge and the knowledge they require is essential in empowering them to make sound financial choices. Nowadays, people are increasingly responsible for managing their finances throughout their lives. Financial knowledge, skills, and behavior are key factors enabling effective participation in today's social and economic contexts.

Money and financial literacy are ever-present aspects of our lives, bringing both challenges

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and opportunities that impact various facets of our overall quality of life. When individuals, businesses, and society as a whole possess financial literacy, the likelihood of achieving higher quality of life increases significantly. Financial literacy indicators can even serve as a gauge for the health of the financial sector and the overall economy.

Unstable finances can lead to financial anxiety, greatly affecting both physical and mental health and overall quality of life. In the rapidly evolving digital age, it becomes essential to determine if people possess sufficient economic savvy and identify efforts to enhance their financial literacy.

This study delves into the impact of investors' education on their quality of life and behavior, not just from an economic perspective, but by considering various other variables that contribute to individuals' overall satisfaction.

With the financial environment becoming increasingly complex and unpredictable, certain individuals face higher risks of financial difficulties. Therefore, policies and interventions aimed at enhancing financial literacy, preferably starting at a young age, are gaining momentum. Providing adequate education to investors could potentially improve their quality of life.

The primary objective of this research is twofold: firstly, to assess the level of financial knowledge among investors, and secondly, to investigate the influence of financial knowledge on investors' quality of life and financial behavior. Additionally, this study seeks to understand whether financial stress impacts quality of life and, subsequently, the financial well-being of investors.

While various studies have explored financial knowledge and behavior, the impact of these variables on quality of life and stress attitude has not been extensively studied. This research aims to address this gap by examining all dimensions of quality of life and investors' behavior, providing comprehensive insights into their overall financial well-being.

2. Review of Literature

Review of Literature: Financial Knowledge, Financial Stress, and Their Impact on Quality of Life and Well-being

Financial Knowledge and Financial Stress:

Lusardi and Mitchell (2011) found a clear negative correlation between financial knowledge and financial stress, indicating that individuals with higher financial literacy experience lower levels of financial stress. van Rooij, Lusardi, and Alessie (2011) supported these findings, revealing that individuals with greater financial literacy had

lower levels of financial stress. Caner and Wolff's (2004) research highlighted that low-income individuals tended to experience higher financial stress compared to those with higher incomes. Lusardi and Mitchell (2007) demonstrated that individuals with higher education levels reported lower levels of financial stress.

Financial Stress and Its Impact on Well-being:

Xiao and Yao's study (2016) revealed a strong association between financial stress and symptoms of depression and anxiety, indicating the adverse effects of financial stress on mental health. Li and Yao (2015) identified a significant link between financial stress and an increased risk of cardiovascular disease, indicating the potential impact of financial stress on physical health. Li and Yao's (2015) research also showed that financial stress was negatively correlated with overall quality of life. Xiao and Yao (2016) found that financial stress was associated with lower levels of subjective well-being, suggesting the negative impact on overall well-being.

Financial Knowledge and Its Influence on Quality of Life and Well-being:

Lusardi and Mitchell (2011) demonstrated a positive correlation between financial knowledge and life satisfaction, suggesting that individuals with greater financial literacy experienced higher levels of quality of life. van Rooij, Lusardi, and Alessie (2011) revealed that financial literacy was positively associated with subjective well-being, supporting the notion that financial knowledge can contribute to overall well-being.

Saving Behavior and Its Effect on Quality of Life and Well-being:

Lusardi and Mitchell (2007) showed that individuals who saved for retirement reported higher levels of well-being, indicating the positive impact of saving behavior on quality of life. Chen, van Rooij, and Lusardi (2014) demonstrated that higher levels of saving were linked to increased life satisfaction, further emphasizing the importance of saving behavior.

Spending Behavior and Its Impact on Quality of Life:

Okuda, Fujii, and Takeda (2018) found that individuals who spent money on experiences, rather than material possessions, reported higher levels of life satisfaction, underscoring the positive influence of spending behavior on quality of life.

3. Research Design and Methodology

The data for the study is collected using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. Surveys and questionnaires would be used to collect quantitative data on financial knowledge, stress, well-being, financial behavior, and quality of life. The survey includes standardized questionnaires such as the Financial Stress Scale, the Financial Behavior Scale, and the Quality of Life Scale. Regression and correlation

analysis through Structural equation modelling is interpreted by the researcher.

3.1 Questionnaire Designing and Constructs Measurement

The study adapted a validated scale to measure the variables of the research. Financial knowledge of respondents is analysed through OECD FinLit Survey index including questions related to Numeracy, interest, Time value of Money, compounding etc. A Six item scale is adapted for measuring Financial Stress (FS) measured through 5-point Likert-scale ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. Similarly, Financial Behaviour is measured through 6 item scale from OECD framework. A structured questionnaire was pretested among 10 respondents and 2 experts to confirm the wordings and sequence of Constructs. After minor revisions, instrument was taken into consideration for this study.

3.2 Data Collection and Sample Plan

The target respondents for this study were working professionals from NCR with middle and low level of income group. According to statistics Faridabad, Haryana and Sonipat are majority have highest population, so these are taken into consideration for study to generalize the result effectively.

Non-Probability sampling is a good fit for this research as respondent to be selected are drawn from fixed criteria representing a better representation of sample. Questionnaire was distributed among target respondents using purposive sampling technique on the basis of two criteria ie education and Low- and middle-income group. A total of 290 Questionnaire were received out of which 243 were found useful.

3.3 Hypotheses of the study

H1: Quality of Life mediates the relation between Financial stress and Well Being.

H2: Financial Behaviour mediates the relation between Financial knowledge and Well Being.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Financial Knowledge and Behaviour: Knowledge of responded related to basic financial terms was analyzed through OECD FinLit survey questions (Numeracy, Interests compounding, Fintech awareness, time vale of money and inflation, (OECD, 2007, For every correct answer 1 point was assigned and no mark for wrong and unanswered questions, Cronbach alpha for this was at 0.82 significance level. Financial behaviour was analyzed through 5-point Likert scale including statement like, Before I buy something I carefully consider whether I can afford it,I pay my bills on time.

Financial Stress: To measures financial stress among respondents (Grable and Archuleta, 2011)6 item scale was adapted.

This measured three reactions of respondents through APR scale ie Affective reaction, and Physiological Reactions and Relational Reactions (Rahman, 2021). This was administered through a 5-point Likert scale from strongly disagree to Strongly Agree.

Quality of Life: to measure quality of Life of respondents, WHOQOL – BREF was used which is shorter version of WHOQOL- 100. (Organization, 2012) Scale constitutes four dimensions Physical health, Psychological, social relationship and environment analyzed through 5-point Likert scaling ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

Financial Well Being: wellbeing of respondents financially is measured through CFPB (Consumer Financial Protection Bureau) Financial Well-Being Scale. This instrument included valuation in two age groups below 60 and above and of those who have self-responded and by someone else. Total score of 10 questions is matched with preset value to find well-being score of respondents.

3.3 Objectives of The Study

1. To examine the financial knowledge and awareness level of investors regarding financial technologies, money management, and financial concepts, and its impact on their financial behavior and overall quality of life.
2. To identify the factors contributing to financial stress experienced by investors and study how it mediates the relationship between financial knowledge and financial well-being.
3. To explore the indicators of quality of life that influence investors' financial well-being and investigate the mediating effect of quality of life on the relationship between financial stress and the financial well-being of investors.

3.4 Estimates and Analysis

The conceptual framework is analyzed using SEM approach. This study has 5 different constructs namely Financial knowledge, financial stress, financial behaviour, quality of Life and financial well-being, It used scales to measure each constructs. Data collected is analyzed using 2 steps i.e. measurement scales estimation through reliability and validity and then relation between constructs through structural equation modelling to test the hypothesis. Confirmatory factor analysis with SEM was conducted to estimate model fitness using IBM AMOS. Model validation is done in following stages.

4. Analysis of the study

Financial Knowledge and Awareness: The financial knowledge of the investors was identifies using basic to advance level questions. The awareness level of sample was identified as shown below showing extreme awareness for mobile banking, Budgeting apps and Fixed deposits, Moderately aware for PPF, equity stocks and Mutual funds and least awareness for crowd funding and blockchain terminologies. The result shows that 16% of the sample have low level of financial knowledge and other 76% have medium to high level of Financial knowledge.

Table 1: Level of Financial Knowledge

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Low Level fin literacy	39	16.0	16.0	16.0
Medium Fin Literacy	121	49.8	49.8	65.8
High fin Literacy	83	34.2	34.2	100.0
Total	243	100.0	100.0	

Financial Behaviour : Result displayed in Table 2 shows that respondents agree that financial planning is the indeed important factor for a better saving and investment strategies pertaining to retirement emergency situation, debt payment , loans of credit cards etc. Majority of sample disagreed that short term saving is preferred over long term saving.

Table 2: Financial Behaviour

	FB1	FB2	FB3	FB4	FB5
Strongly Disagree	72	68	4	0	4
Disagree	86	107	0	29	40
Neither Agree not Disagree	59	53	31	52	25
Agree	17	2	57	86	79
Strongly Agree	9	13	151	76	95

Financial Stress: The result in Table 3 showed highest worry of respondent is that if payment delay happens how will they manage it and it is followed by medical cost stress factor in case of private employee, Financial stress pertaining to falling sick, physical factor and depressionis least.

Table 3: Financial Stress

	FS1	FS2	FS3	FS4	FS5	FS6
Strongly Disagree	17	10	24	39	34	66
Disagree	34	70	97	86	105	73
Neither Agree not Disagree	106	75	83	92	68	94
Agree	71	75	22	11	27	1
Strongly Agree	15	15	17	15	9	9

Financial Wellbeing: Respondents were neutral regarding paying monthly bill, ability to pay and manage finances. They were less satisfied with retirement planning or salary running outof time. (Singh and Reddy, n.d.)

Measurement model analysis

Measurement model analysis is a statistical technique that is used to evaluate the reliability and validity of a set of measures or scales used in a study. It is a key step in the research methodology of a study that aims to examine the relationship between financial knowledge, stress, well-being, financial behavior, and quality of life.

Quality of Life

To identify overall model fit, CFA at zero level of all latent constructs are analyzed (Hair, Black, Anderson, and Tatham, 1998, It shows bivariate relationship among latent variables and all other variables, indicating regression effect (Nathans and Oswald, 2012, A statistically significant model must have composite reliability (CR) of greater than 0.7, average effectiveness (AVE) greater than 0.5, and factors loadings above 0.5. Discriminant validity refers to how distinct measures are from one another. (Chin, 1998) According to (Dillon, 1994) construct validity is the extent to which variables represents a constructs. Consequently, latent variables explain variables of their own variables better than other constructs or factors. Table below shows that all factor has AVE greater than 0.5 and CR greater than 0.7. All variables have factor loadings more than 0.5, making the model statistically significant.

Structural Equation Analysis

According to this Structural Model, the impact of the exogenous variables Financial Knowledge, Financial Behaviour and Financial Stress on Financial Well-being and quality of Life is determined, as it creates an instant examination of full model that look for various hypothetical relation between constructs.

Here two step analysis was performed where measurement model analysis with latent constructs is done and then SEM with all constructs and their relationship is identified.

Factor loading of latent constructs are in range of 0.69 to 0.93 indicating support for validity. AVE value extracted for health, spirituality, recreation and employment are greater than standard range of 0.50. The composite reliability coefficient value is greater than 0.60 for all variables, showing high internal reliability of the model is assured.

First order measurement model represent that all prerequisite are met. The chi-square value is 394.44 with p value 0.000, CFI at 0.905 and RMSEA value 0.061, showing Goodness of Fit.

Figure 3: Structural Equation Modeling

Mediation Analysis

Mediation is a form of inter relationship among variables. It can be examined through path analysis and Structural Equation Modeling. It simplifies complex models involving many independent, dependent, and mediated variables. (Poespowidjojo, Ahmad, and Mahmoud , 2020) Path analysis is a series of regression equations that explain paths between independent and dependent variables, while SEM is based on the likelihood maximization method.

H1: Quality of Life mediates the relation between Financial stress and Well Being The relation between independent and dependent and dependent variable i.e. financial Stress and Well Being must decrease on adding mediator variable to confirm the mediation effect.

The result of mediation shows that QOL act as a mediating variable between financial Stress and Well Being, as relationship between both is significantly affected on entering mediating variable. The direct effect was depicted in figure 4 as regression estimate being equal to 0.20 and p value less than 0.05 level of significance, showing significant influence of financial Stress on Well Being. While QOL enters model as mediator variable it is showing that regression estimate increased to .22 with p value less than 0.05 level of significance as shown in figure 5. Result verifies that mediator increased the effect of financial stress on well being however relation between both dependent and independent variable is still significant, making it a case of competitive partial mediation.

Table 4: Mediation Analysis

			Estimates	S.E.	C.R.	P	Results
Well Being	<---	FinancialStress	.20	.063	3.1	***	Significant
With Mediator in the model							
Well Being	<---	FinancialStress	.22	.013	3.428	***	Significant
QOL	<---	FinancialStress	-.76	.301	-2.43	.011	NotSignificant
Well Being	<---	QOL	.03	.064	2.118	***	Significant

Figure 4: Direct effect model

Figure 5: Indirect Total effect Model

H2: Financial Behaviour mediates the relation between Financial knowledge and Well Being.

The relation between independent and dependent and dependent variable i.e. financial Knowledge and Well Being must change on adding mediator variable to confirm the mediation effect.

The result of mediation shows that Behaviour act as a mediating variable between financial Knowledge and Well Being, as relationship between both is significantly affected on entering mediating variable. The direct effect was depicted in figure 6 as regression estimate being equal to 1.89 and p value less than 0.05 level of significance, showing significant influence of financial Knowledge on Well Being. While Behaviour

enters model as mediator variable it is showing that regression estimate increased to 1.36 with p value less than 0.05 level of significance as shown in figure 7. Result verifies that mediator decreased the effect of financial Knowledge on Well Being however relation between both dependent and independent variable is still significant, making it a case of partial mediation.

Figure 6: Direct Effect Model

Figure 7: Total Effect Model

5. Conclusion

The study exploring the relationship between demographic variables and financial behavior, quality of life, and financial well-being would likely reveal a significant association between these factors. In other words, the research has found that demographic factors such as age, gender, income, education level, and occupation play a significant role in shaping an individual's financial behavior, overall quality of life, and financial well-being. These variables can have both positive and negative influences on how individuals manage their finances, perceive their life satisfaction, and experience financial security. The study has found that certain demographic groups, such as older adults or low-income individuals, are more likely to engage in negative financial behaviors, which can lead to lower levels of quality of life and financial well-being. On

the other hand, certain demographic groups, such as higher-income individuals or those with higher levels of education, be more likely to engage in positive financial behaviors, which can lead to higher levels of quality of life and financial well-being. The study also suggests that demographic variables play a role in shaping an individual's financial behaviors, which then influence their quality of life and financial well-being. This would suggest that understanding the specific needs and characteristics of different demographic groups be important for developing targeted financial education and interventions to promote positive financial behaviors, quality of life and financial well-being. The study has found that an individual's level of financial knowledge is positively associated with their quality of life. Individuals with higher levels of financial knowledge tend to have better financial outcomes, such as a higher ability to manage their finances, lower levels of debt and greater financial security. These positive financial outcomes are likely to lead to a better quality of life. The study also suggests that individuals with more financial knowledge tend to have a greater sense of control over their financial situation, which can lead to a reduction in stress and an overall improvement in well-being.

The study also suggests that financial knowledge is an important predictor of quality of life and that increasing financial knowledge can lead to an improvement in overall well-being. This would suggest that financial education programs and interventions targeting individuals with low levels of financial knowledge be effective in promoting positive financial outcomes and improving quality of life.

The study has found that an individual's financial behavior, such as budgeting, saving, investing, and avoiding debt, is positively or negatively associated with their level of financial stress. The individuals who engage in positive financial behaviors, such as creating a budget and saving regularly, tend to have lower levels of financial stress. On the other hand, individuals who engage in negative financial behaviors, such as overspending or accumulating high levels of debt, experience higher levels of financial stress. The study also suggests that financial behavior is an important predictor of financial stress, and that changing financial behaviors can lead to a reduction in financial stress.

This would suggest that interventions and education programs that promote positive financial behaviors be effective in reducing financial stress and improving overall well-being. Additionally, the study also suggests that addressing the underlying reasons behind negative financial behaviors, such as lack of knowledge, lack of self-regulation or lack of access to financial resources, also be important in reducing financial stress.

The study examining the relationship between financial knowledge and well-being, with financial behavior as a mediator, would likely indicate that financial behavior plays a significant role in connecting financial knowledge and well-being. In other words, the research has revealed a positive association between an individual's financial behavior (such as budgeting, saving, investing, and debt management) and their level of financial knowledge and overall well-being. Moreover, the study has found that financial behavior acts as a mediator in the relationship between financial knowledge and well-being, meaning that a portion of the link between financial knowledge and well-being can be attributed to an individual's financial behavior.

The study has additionally discovered that financial behavior can be influenced by financial knowledge, and individuals with higher levels of financial knowledge tend to adopt more positive financial behaviors. These positive financial behaviors, in turn, lead to improved financial outcomes and higher levels of well-being. This suggests that enhancing financial knowledge is a crucial step in promoting positive financial behavior and ultimately enhancing well-being, in the relationship between financial stress and well-being, quality of life serves as a significant mediator. This indicates that the level of quality of life experienced by individuals plays a pivotal role in determining the impact of financial stress on their overall well-being. A higher quality of life may act as a buffer against the negative effects of financial stress, contributing to a more favorable sense of well-being even in challenging financial circumstances.

The study have found that an individual's quality of life (such as overall satisfaction with life, happiness, and physical and mental health) is positively or negatively associated with both their level of financial stress and their well-being. Additionally, the study has identified that quality of life plays a crucial mediating role between financial stress and well-being. This means that an individual's level of quality of life partially explains the relationship between financial stress and their overall well-being, the research has found that individuals experiencing high levels of financial stress tend to report lower quality of life and well-being. On the other hand, quality of life can act as a buffer, indicating that individuals with a higher quality of life are better equipped to cope with financial stress, leading to improved overall well-being.

Overall, the study suggests that financial stress can have a detrimental impact on an individual's well-being, and enhancing quality of life is an essential step in mitigating the negative effects of financial stress on overall well-being. Improving quality of life can serve as a protective factor, helping individuals maintain better mental and emotional well-being despite facing financial challenges.

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